

Preticial Sexual Behavior in Adolescents in the City of Lhokseumawe

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Abstract— This research is to see the level of premarital sex. This study uses descriptive statistics involving 182 people who were taken from all those who participated in this study are teenagers at the X Junior High School in Lhokseumawe City. Participants in this study were 12 to 16 years. The results showed that the average premarital sexual behavior in adolescents in SMP X was appropriate in the low category.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the results of a survey conducted by the National Family Planning Coordinating Board (Mintarti, Basuki, Novianti, 2013) found that the rise of promiscuity among adolescents will be questioned. The survey results show that 52% of adolescents in Medan, 51% in Jabodetabek, 54% in Surabaya, and 47% in Bandung adolescents claimed to have had premarital sex. Data obtained from the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) and the Ministry of Health (Dahafni & Tahlil, 2013) show that approximately 62.7% of adolescents in Indonesia have had premarital sex. Related to premarital sexual behavior among adolescents today must be a serious concern for all parties involved.

Premarital sexual behavior by adolescents can produce some negativity. Psychological negative effects can cause feelings of anger, fear, anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, self-confidence and sin. In addition, social benefits obtained by adolescents include being ostracized by the community, as well as dropping out of school among adolescent girls who experience pregnancy. Another negative impact of the physical situation is the development of STDs, HIV or AIDS (Sarwono, 2011).

According to Sarwono (2012) the development of sexual activity in adolescents begins with the establishment of interactions with the opposite sex, both interactions between friends and dating with a partner. When teens are dating their partners, teenagers discuss the aspects that are then expressed in various ways. The influence of sexy impulses in adolescents is accompanied by a sense of attraction towards types, making teens begin to divert attention to the opposite type.

II. OBJECTION AND METHOD

This research is to see the level of premarital sex. This study involved 182 people who participated who gathered all the participants in this study were teenagers in the X Junior High School in Lhokseumawe City. Participants in this study were 12 to 16 years. The measuring instrument used is the

section scale proposed by Fuhrmann (1990). This scale is arranged with a type of scale similar to a scale consisting of five choices of answers: Very Frequently (SS), Frequently (S), Ever (P), and Never (TP). For profitable items, answer answers are as follows: SS = 4, S = 3, P = 2, TP = 1. The higher the score obtained, the higher the section performed by the individual. The higher the score obtained, the lower the section performed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that the sections consist of high, medium and low categories (Fuhrmann, 1990). Table 1 about premarital sex

Percentage Frequency Category

Height 2 1.5%

Medium 2 1.5%

Low 128 97.0%

Table shows participants who were at the level of the premarital section who did 128 people, participants who were in the high category 2 people. This shows that the average participant in this study behaved in the moderate category of premarital sex section.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study is to look at the category of sexual protection in adolescents. The average participant in this studio has a sexy behavior at a mild level, that is, individuals have not engaged in premarital behavior.

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